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THE COMBINED EFFECT OF MOISTURE AND TEST TEMPERATURE ON THE PSEUDO-DUCTILITY OF THIN-PLY HYBRID COMPOSITES

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Carbon/epoxy composites: STIFF, STRONG

and LIGHTWEIGHT!

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BUT failure is CATASTROPHIC

DUCTILITY is needed for safety

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High Performance
Ductile Composite Technology-
HiPerDuCT Programme

Introduction

- **High performance composites: stiff and strong, but failure is sudden and brittle with little warning and poor residual strength**
- **Pseudo-ductility with an intrinsic safety margin could change design approach and offer major benefits**
- **Excellent pseudo-ductility demonstrated first with UD glass/carbon interlayer hybrids in tension [1,2]***
- **Visible damage:**

-**Overload indicator** [3]

The concept is then adopted for:

- **UD IM/HM carbon hybrids** [4]
- **QI IM/UHM carbon hybrids** [5]

*See references at the end of the document

Key challenges

- To study the effect of **test temperature and moisture** on the ductility mechanisms in UD carbon/glass hybrids in tension
- **Fragmentation and delamination** to be assessed separately

Specimen design

Delamination:

$$G_{II} = \frac{\varepsilon_{2b}^2 E_2 t_2 (2E_1 t_1 + E_2 t_2)}{8E_1 t_1}$$

Glass layer thickness:

$$t_1 > \frac{\varepsilon_{2b} E_2 t_2}{2E_1 (\varepsilon_{1b} - \varepsilon_{2b})}$$

Lay-up sequence	Carbon layer	Nominal thickness	Energy release rate at carbon fibre failure strain (1.6%) ^a	Minimum vs. nominal glass/epoxy layer thickness	Initial modulus ^a
		[mm]	[N/mm]	[mm]	[GPa]
[S-glass ₁ /TC35 ₂ / S-glass ₁]	Continuous	0.358	0.480	0.045/0.155	54.7
[S-glass ₂ /TC35 ₄ / S-glass ₂]	Discontinuous	0.716	0.959	0.090/0.310	54.7

^aCalculated using manufacturer's data

Test method

Environmental chamber

Mechanical wedge grip

Test specimen with markers for strain measurement

Video-extensometer

Test temperatures:

-50°C, 25°C, 80°C

Wet conditioning:
60°C, 90% RH

Hybrid specimens:
1500 hour conditioning

S-glass/epoxy:
125/500/1000/1500 h
conditioning

Evaluation of pseudo-ductility

Results- Water uptake

Process modelling:

$$\Delta m(t) = \Delta m_{\infty} \cdot \left(1 - e^{(-A \cdot t)^{\left(\frac{1}{2K}\right)}}\right)^K$$

Continuous hybrid
(average of 16 specimens)

Discontinuous hybrid
(average of 16 specimens)

Results- Continuous hybrid specimens

- Change of failure mode due to conditioning
- Significant drop in damage initiation strain

Results- Monolithic S-glass/epoxy specimens

- Water uptake of S-glass/epoxy is higher than that of the hybrids
- Failure strain is reduced by 30% after 1000 hours

Hot-wet conditioning: 60°C, 90% relative humidity, 125/500/1000/1500 hours

Tensile testing at room temperature (25°C)

Results- Discontinuous hybrid specimens

- Failure became less stable due to moisture
- Glass layer strength reduced

Conclusions

- Unconditioned hybrid specimens showed pseudo-ductile stress-strain response between -50°C and 80°C : the continuous specimens fragmented, the discontinuous specimens showed stable delamination between the glass and carbon layers
- Water uptake processes of monolithic S-glass/epoxy and both hybrid specimen types were investigated in detail
- A suitable function was found to model the water uptake process that fitted well to the experimental data
- Wet conditioning changed the damage mode of the continuous hybrid specimens from pseudo-ductile to catastrophic failure
- Moisture sensitivity of glass/epoxy layers was found to be responsible for the lack of pseudo-ductility in the case of continuous hybrids
- Increasing test temperature decreased the mode II fracture toughness of the discontinuous specimens
- Wet conditioning decreased the mode II fracture toughness further at all temperatures

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